

PROBABILISTIC MODELS FOR HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Data are presented for the strength of simple impregnated bundles of carbon fibres and similar bundles in a model hybrid laminate. There is a pronounced strength enhancement in the hybrid. The probabilistic models for composite strength are extended by an argument which considers different properties for the sheath and core regions of the bundle.

INTRODUCTION

Probabilistic models for composite materials were introduced to explain some of the properties of parallel-fibre composites some twenty years ago, and these concepts have recently been developed both theoretically and experimentally. Hybrid composites pose more complex problems than simple fibre-matrix combinations in view of the non-uniform stress distributions between the two phases of the hybrid. Experimentally, however, hybrids afford the opportunity to study some aspects of failure in more detail than is possible in simple systems, and this has led to an improvement in the understanding of the failure processes of composites in general.

A statistical theory of strength of materials was developed by Weibull [1], based on the 'weakest link' concept. The starting point of this theory was the notion that the strength of a material may be represented as the weakest strength of a large number of strengths. Assuming the components to have (independent) random strengths, a consistent family of probability distributions was derived. The best

known of this family is the (two-parameter) Weibull distribution

$$\Pr(X > x) = \exp[-V (x/x_0)^w] \quad (1)$$

for the strength X of a material of volume V , x_0 is a scaling parameter; the 'characteristic stress' and w the Weibull exponent or 'shape' parameter.

Weibull's theory is not directly applicable to composite materials because the parallel-fibre structure violates the weakest-link principle. Daniels [2] proposed a statistical theory for a bundle of threads (see Daniels and Skyrme [3] for some modern developments) but their theory assumed uniform stress concentrations which is also not an appropriate assumption for composites. The first probabilistic theories for composites as such were those of Rosen [4] and Zweben [5]. The two key assumptions of their theories are; (i) in a direction parallel to the fibres, the stress concentrations around a flaw are restricted to a very short length of the composite, estimated to be around 5-10 fibre diameters, (ii) across the width of a composite, the stress concentrations around a broken fibre are restricted to a small group of fibres around the the region of failure. The mathematical theory of such systems was developed in detail first by Harlow and Phoenix [6,7] and later by Smith et al. [8], resulting in accurate mathematical approximations for the probability of failure in such systems. Two key features emerged from these theoretical analyses. First was the notion of a critical flaw number i^* , typically less than 10, with the interpretation that a group of i^* adjacent failed fibres was sufficient to fail the system in view of the the localised stress concentrations and the smallness of the i^* . These notions together imply that, if the Weibull distribution (1) holds for single fibres, then it is also expected to hold for composite materials, with the shape parameter w multiplied by the critical flaw number i^* . An alternative viewpoint was provided by Batdorf [9], who obtained similar though not identical conclusions from an analysis based on critical groups of adjacent failures or 'i-plets'.

Experimental work at Surrey (Manders and Bader [10], Bader and Priest [11]) has permitted a critical evaluation of how these theories perform when applied to real materials. Hybrid composites have been constructed from a central core of parallel high-modulus carbon fibres embedded in a glass-epoxy combination. In addition, the carbon fibres have been studied singly, and in the form of impregnated bundles (a bundle of parallel

fibres impregnated with epoxy resin). For all three types of material, the Weibull distribution (1) was found to fit well to the experimental data, with shape parameter w about 6 for the single fibres, 20 for the impregnated bundles and 30 for the hybrid bundles. Since large w corresponds to small variability in the distribution, this confirms that the composites show much less statistical variability than single fibres. Moreover, the mean failure stress turned out to be substantially greater for the hybrid composites than for the impregnated bundles, implying a 'hybrid effect' which cannot be explained by a simple rule of mixtures. Watson and Smith (12) presented a more detailed statistical analysis of these data, questioning the validity of the distribution (1) when applied to bundles of different lengths, but otherwise confirming the Bader-Priest analysis, in particular with reference to the existence of a hybrid effect. They were unable, however, to explain the hybrid effect in terms of the statistical properties of the materials.

For the present study, this previous work has been extended both experimentally and theoretically. The experimental work has included a considerable amount of new work on carbon-glass hybrids. On the theoretical side, we propose some modifications of the existing theoretical models to allow for different stress concentrations in impregnated and hybrid bundles. These allow us to provide a theoretical explanation of the hybrid effect, although there must still be reservations concerning the validity of some of the assumptions used.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The materials studied were a carbon-fibre and simple and hybrid composites formed from the carbon-fibre, glass-fibre and an epoxy-resin.

The carbon-fibre was taken from a single spool of 1000 filament (1k) tow of 'Celion 1000' supplied by the Celanese Corporation. The fibres were the 'high-strength' type prepared from poly-acrylonitrile precursor, fibre diameter is approximately $8\mu\text{m}$ and strain-to-failure a little over 1%. The material was supplied in 1979 and is not representative of current production. The glass-fibre was an E-glass provided by Owens-Corning (UK) Ltd., it was supplied in rovings of 1200 and 2400 tex (approximately 1750 and 3500 filaments), the fibres were approximately $20\mu\text{m}$ in diameter.

The resin was formulated from a standard bisphenonol-A epoxy-resin (Shell 828) cured with nadic-methyl-anhydride (NMA) with an amine accelerator (Shell K61B). This has a very low viscosity, which simplifies the impregnation of the fibre bundles and is cured at 100°C for 3 hours with a post-cure at 150°C for a further 3 hours. It cures to form a transparent pale-amber coloured solid.

TESTING

Tensile tests were conducted to determine the strength of single carbon-fibres, of bundles of these fibres impregnated with an epoxy-resin to form a composite ligament and of hybrid-composites containing similar carbon-fibre ligaments.

The single filaments were tested using the conventional 'window card' technique. The fibre diameter was measured by a laser diffraction technique and the tensile strength was calculated from the maximum force recorded and the measured cross-section. The strain to failure was not measured but the fibre modulus was determined from the tests on the impregnated bundles.

Impregnated bundles were prepared by passing 1, 5 or 10 carbon-tows through a bath of the liquid resin and then partially curing in a continuous process. Suitable lengths of this impregnated tow were then cut, end tags were affixed and they were then finally cured to form cylindrical ligaments of the selected gauge-lengths, which were from 10 to 300mm. These were tested to failure in a similar manner to that described for the single filaments. Stress-strain measurements were made on a number of these impregnated tows so that the Young's modulus of the fibres could be calculated.

The hybrid test pieces were made by taking lengths of the partially-cured impregnated carbon-tows and incorporating them into sheets formed from unidirectional glass-fibre rovings. These were then impregnated with the resin and cured. Test coupons were then cut from the sheets. These were typically 250mm long, 20mm wide and 2mm thick, with a single carbon-fibre ligament running through the centre of the section (fig.1). These test-pieces were then set up in the testing machine with a camera arranged to photograph the gauge section. The test-piece was illuminated with polarised light and a crossed-polar set up on the camera lens. When

Figure 1. TEST PIECES

A. Window card for testing the single filaments. The sides of the card are cut away as indicated when the fibre has been positioned in the testing machine.

B. Impregnated-bundle test-piece

C. Hybrid-bundle test-piece. The carbon-fibre bundle is visible through the transparent glass/epoxy. The system of notional gauge lengths is indicated.

the test-piece was extended the carbon ligament would fail and the stress discontinuity around the point of failure caused a photo-elastic effect in the surrounding glass-fibre/epoxy-resin material, this was recorded on film. It was thus possible to record the position and strain corresponding to each fracture of the carbon ligament. Each test was generally continued until the strain was approximately 2.0%, at this strain up to 50 individual ligament failures might be recorded in a single test piece. The data collected relates only to failure of the carbon-fibre portion of the hybrid, the tests were not continued to the point when the glass-fibre component failed.

The statistical analysis of the data is based on plots of probability of failure against failure stress fitted to a Weibull 2-parameter model. It should be noted that in the single-fibre tests the force at failure was recorded and the diameter of each fibre measured. In the impregnated bundle tests the force at failure was measured, and this has been reduced to the fibre stress using the average fibre diameter, the number of fibres in the bundle and assuming that the load carried by the resin matrix was negligible. However for the hybrid bundles the strain at failure was measured and reduced to fibre stress using the average fibre modulus. For the purposes of the analysis the hybrid test piece was divided into a

number of notional gauge lengths. A failure could then be assigned to the appropriate gauge length. A single test-piece was thus considered to consist of 1 x 200mm, 2 x 100mm, 4 x 50mm and 10 x 20mm individual gauge lengths. The test was continued until at least one failure had been registered in each of these lengths, ie a minimum of 20 failures. This technique ensured that the maximum amount of data could be extracted from each test-piece.

Microscopy

In parallel with the mechanical testing, the modes of failure were studied using various microscopy techniques. These included examination of fracture surfaces and sections taken from the impregnated tows and extensive studies of sections cut from the hybrid specimens. It should be noted that when a composite fails in tension a large amount of strain energy must be dissipated. This usually results in extensive secondary fracture and often complete fragmentation and splitting of the test-piece. It is thus almost impossible to identify the site of the original failure. The hybrid specimens are unique, in that the failure of the carbon ligament is contained by the surrounding glass/epoxy material and the fracture is, thus, preserved for further examination.

The experimental data is summarised in Table 1 and two sets of cumulative distribution curves for impregnated bundles and hybrids respectively are shown in figure 2. The extent of the hybrid effect is seen as the shift between these two sets of curves. Figure 3 is a plot of \ln strength vs. \ln volume. It shows data for both bundles and hybrids of all lengths and bundle sizes tested. The linear relationship shows approximate conformation to the weak-link hypothesis and the vertical shift between the curves is the hybrid effect.

Figure 4 is a photomicrograph of a polished section through a carbon-tow failure in a hybrid test-piece. The spatial relationship between the individual fibre failures is clearly shown. Several of the fibre failures have not contributed to the tow failure. These are the hairline failures. When the tow failed there was a local relaxation of strain which led to gaps about $5\mu\text{m}$ wide forming between the broken ends of the fibres.

THEORY

There are two main parts to the modelling: first, a mathematical representation of the stress concentrations around a failure or group of

failures in the fibres, and secondly, calculations of the probability of failure for such stress concentrations. The stress concentrations depend, in the first place, on an ineffective length δ (fig. 5) which represents the length of the composite, in the direction of the fibres, over which the stress concentrations occur. This is typically believed to be around 5 fibre diameters, ie $40\mu\text{m}$, though there is considerable uncertainty about this. The assumption leads to a 'chain of bundles' model, in which the bundle of fibres is broken up into independent sub-bundles, each of length equal to the ineffective length. Then, within each sub-bundle,

TABLE J
Experimental data from tensile tests on fibres and bundles

TEST	GAUGE LENGTH	CHARACTERISTIC STRESS	WEIBULL EXPONENT	MEAN WEIBULL EXPONENT	NUMBER OF TESTS	NORMALISED CHARACTERISTIC STRESS	HYBRID EFFECT
	L(mm)	σ'_0 (GPa)	w	\bar{w}		σ'_0	%
A							
<u>Single Carbon</u>	1	4.77			57	1.00	
<u>Fibre*</u>	10	3.16		5.6	64	0.66	
8 μm dia	20	2.79			70	0.58	
	50	2.37			66	0.49	
B							
<u>Impregnated</u>	20	2.75	26		25	0.57	
<u>Tow</u>	50	2.86	26	28	26	0.60	
1000 filaments	100	2.78	36		28	0.58	
	200	2.76	25		51	0.58	
5000 filaments	20	2.73	41		14	0.57	
	50	2.66	26	29.5	14	0.56	
	100	2.62	25		14	0.55	
	200	2.57	26		14	0.54	
10000 filaments	20	2.70	50		9	0.57	
	50	2.75	63	45	13	0.58	
	100	2.64	33		10	0.55	
	200	2.63	35		14	0.55	
C							
<u>Hybrid Tows**</u>	20	3.77	30		151	0.79	37
	50	3.70	30	29.5	61	0.78	29
1000 filaments	100	3.65	28		29	0.77	31
	200	3.58	30		16	0.75	30
5000 filaments	20	3.65	21		92	0.77	34
	50	3.56	19	27	39	0.75	34
	100	3.44	33		20	0.72	31
	200	3.39	34		10	0.71	32
10000 filaments	20	3.60	32		59	0.75	33
	50	3.56	31	33	37	0.75	29
	100	3.51	28		18	0.74	33
	200	3.43	42		9	0.72	30

* Data from Bader and Priest (11) with maximum likelihood analysis of Watson and Smith (12)

** Stress corrected for thermal stress

Figure 2. CUMULATIVE DISTRIBUTION CURVES FOR IMPREGNATED AND HYBRID BUNDLES

The symbols indicate the different gauge lengths. The length/strength effect is not very great but the hybrid-effect is the horizontal shift between the two sets of curves.

Figure 3. WEIBULL PLOT FOR IMPREGNATED AND HYBRID BUNDLES

In this figure the natural log. of x_0 is plotted against nat. log. of volume (both normalised to 1mm single-fibre data). The fitted lines indicate an approximate compliance with the principle of weak-link scaling. The shape parameter w , (slope = $-1/w$), is approximately 50. The vertical shift is the hybrid-effect. The top scale indicates the bundle size (1,5,10k) and gauge length respectively, eg 1/20.

some assumptions have to be made about the stress concentrations on the surviving fibres surrounding a group of failed fibres. Theoretical calculations of these stress concentrations were made by Hedgepeth [13], Hedgepeth and Van Dyke [14], but these and other theoretical results are too complicated for the calculations we want to perform, so some simplified models have been adopted. Following Bader and Pitkethly [15], we assume that the stress around a group of i failures is concentrated on

$$n(i) = f \sqrt{i} \quad (2)$$

fibres, where f is an adjustable parameter, and that the corresponding stress concentration on these $n(i)$ fibres is

$$k(i) = 1 + i/n(i) = (f + \sqrt{i})/f. \quad (3)$$

For the failure probability of single fibres, we assume the Weibull distribution in the form

$$\Pr(X > x) = \exp[-L (x/x_0)^W] \quad (4)$$

for the strength X of a single fibre of length L . This distribution is fitted to the single-fibre experimental data, and then applied with $L = \delta$, the ineffective length.

Putting these ideas together, it is possible to calculate (approximately) the expected number $Q(i)$ of failed i -plets in the material. Assuming a Poisson distribution, we then obtain $[1 - \exp(-Q(i))]$ as the probability of at least one failed i -plet in the material. Setting $i=i^*$, the critical flaw number, we obtain an approximation to the probability of failure of the material. This may, in turn, be approximated by the Weibull distribution for bundle failure

$$\Pr(X > x) = \exp[-L (x/x_0)^{i^*w}] = \exp[-(x/x_L^*)^{i^*w}] \text{ (say) (5)}$$

in which x_L^* is defined as the applied stress for which

$$Q(i^*) = 1. \quad (6)$$

There is still the question of how to determine i^* . Bader and Pitkethly (15) proposed defining i^* to be first i for which $Q(i+1) > Q(i)$. Since $Q(i)$ is found in practice first to decrease and then to increase, as i increases, this is equivalent to saying that we define i^* as the value of i which minimises $Q(i)$, or alternatively which minimises the calculated probability of failure. In the case of one-dimensional nearest neighbour stress concentrations, this rule was given a theoretical justification by Smith (16). We therefore retain it here.

Figure 4. PHOTOMICROGRAPH OF A SECTION THROUGH A FAILURE IN A HYBRID TEST-PIECE

Note the path of the fracture through the fibre-bundle. The hair-line cracks are independent fibre failures.

Modifications for hybrid composites

So far we have made no distinction between hybrid and impregnated composites. The preceding set up, however, gives us the wherewithal to do so, since the different stress concentrations may be represented by different values of f and, perhaps, also varying δ . In particular, we are led to the possibility that the stress concentrations may not be the same in all parts of the bundle. We consider a 'core-sheath' model in which a different value of f applies in an outer sheath of fibres, one or possibly two fibres thick, from a core which contains the remaining fibres of the bundle. In an impregnated bundle, the stress concentrations are expected to be higher on the surface than in the middle because fewer fibres are involved in load sharing, so we use a lower value of f for the sheath than the core. In contrast, in a hybrid the glass surrounding the carbon bundle has a protective effect, which may result in a higher f for the sheath than the core. Some calculations based on varying the values of w, δ, f (core) and f (sheath) are given in Table 2. These show hybrid effects comparable with those observed experimentally. The computed values are strongly dependent on the chosen value of δ and to a lesser extent on w . The value of the load sharing parameter, f , is also important. The best fit between experimental and computed data is when $\delta = 10\mu\text{m}$, $f(\text{sheath}) = 2$ and $f(\text{core}) = 8$.

DISCUSSION

Core-sheath arguments

In the simple Weibull model of a brittle material, the tensile strength is a function of the probability of the test section containing a critical flaw. Thus, the larger the section, the greater the probability of it containing a flaw and, thus, the lower the predicted strength. The concept of 'weak-link scaling' (as in (1)) is based on the volume of material, and doubling either the length or the cross-sectional area of the sample should have similar effects. This is also illustrated by figure 3 where impregnated 1k tows of 200mm length appear to have a similar strength to a 40mm length of the 5k tow, both containing a similar volume of fibre. Similar agreement is noted when different lengths of similar sized fibres or bundles are compared, though Watson and Smith [12] showed that the agreement is much better for single fibres than for bundles. One reason for this behaviour is that there are different

TABLE 2

Comparison of experimental and computed values of characteristic stress and critical i-plet order

BUNDLE SIZE	EXPERIMENTAL NORMALISED STRENGTH σ'_o		COMPUTED STRENGTH								
			δ	w	f	BUNDLE High Surface SCF*		HYBRID Low Surface SCF**			
	Bundle	Hybrid	(μm)			σ'_o	$i_{(\text{crit})}$	σ'_o	$i_{(\text{crit})}$		
A 50mm 1K	0.60	0.78	10	6	1	0.60	4	-	-		
					2	0.71	5	-	-		
					4	-	-	0.75	7		
					8	-	-	0.79	9		
			10	12	1	0.59	3	-	-		
					2	0.70	3	-	-		
					4	-	-	0.75	5		
					8	-	-	0.81	7		
B 50mm 1K	0.60	0.78	10	6	2	0.71	5	-	-		
					20	6	2	0.65	5	-	-
					30	6	2	0.61	5	-	-
					40	6	2	0.60	5	-	-
			10	6	8	-	-	0.79	9	-	-
					20	6	8	-	-	0.71	8
					30	6	8	-	-	0.67	8
					40	6	8	-	-	0.64	8

* Assumes a sheath of 120 fibres subject to high SCF

** Assumes uniform low SCF throughout 1000 filament bundle

distributions of flaws on the surface and within the volume of the materials. It is virtually certain that the strength of the fibres is dominated by surface flaws but it would be extremely difficult to test experimentally, requiring fibres of different diameters but identical flaw distribution. In the bundle, the strength-controlling flaw is considered to be a critical accumulation of broken fibres, ie an i-plet. It may be argued that a surface i-plet is more severe than a core i-plet. This would then imply that a small bundle, with relatively greater surface to volume, would be relatively weaker than a larger bundle. This effect would be superimposed on the normal size effect, and would mean that simple 'weak-link scaling' between bundles of different diameter would not be expected.

Figure 5. STRESS DISTRIBUTION AROUND A BROKEN FIBRE

It is assumed that the interaction is confined to the nearest neighbour to the broken fibre. The ineffective length δ is indicated, together with the concept of a shorter zone δ' of higher stress.

The core-sheath argument also goes some way towards explaining the observed hybrid effect. In the hybrid the surface of the bundle is buried within the glass/epoxy phase of the material. The 'surface' of the carbon-fibre bundle is no longer a true surface and the stress redistribution around a 'surface' i-plet will extend into the the glass, thus reducing its severity. In fact the severity of these i-plets may be reduced to a level even below that of the core i-plets because the glass fibres, although of lower elastic modulus than the carbon, are of much greater diameter and therefore greater absolute stiffness in the micro-mechanics sense. The failure strain of the glass is also much greater than that of the carbon, so that the i-plet can never grow into the glass phase.

The theory does not explain the whole of the hybrid effect but there is independent evidence of thermal and elastic constraint effects [16] and it appears that a combination of these effects and the probabilistic arguments provide a viable explanation of the hybrid effect.

There is also the possibility that the core-sheath theory, combined with improved methods of calculation of the probability of failure, may

help to explain the observed discrepancies from the weakest-link model. Watson and Smith [12] found that a model of form

$$\Pr(X > x) = \exp[L^\alpha(x/x_2)^{1/\alpha}], \quad (7)$$

with $\alpha \approx 0.5$, fitted the experimental data much better than the usual weakest-link model with $\alpha = 1$. Our calculations are consistent with α about 0.75, again explaining some of the effect but not all of it.

The present theory provides a plausible and qualitative explanation for the observed hybrid effect. Its shortcoming is that the values used for δ and the load sharing factor f cannot be substantiated independently. The experimental figures can only be matched if δ is set at a very low value (10-20 μm), and the sheath f at between 1 and 2. This is a very severe condition. These values may be justified to some extent by the argument that the stress concentration would be highest in the middle of the load transfer zone (figure 5), so that although there is evidence that the zone extends overall about 5 fibre diameters (40 μm) either side of the fibre fracture, the stress is higher over the central region δ' and this is the 'effective' region. In a real composite the fibres are distributed in a more or less random manner across the section so that some fibres touch whilst others are well separated. The probability of the i-plet growing will be much greater for these very close neighbours and, thus, a more severe stress concentration (lower values of f) may apply.

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